

Summary of ash sequence data generated by Richard Buggs's research groups at Queen Mary University of London and Royal Botanic Gardens Kew

v. 1.0

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Table 1: Ash species reference genomes

Species	Individual (sequencing code, accession/genotype number)	Reads on ENA	NCBI Assembly	Publication
<i>Fraxinus excelsior</i>	FRAX00 2451S	Project: PRJEB4958 Sample: ERS370607 Experiments: ERX1470833- ERX1470834; ERX344708-ERX344729	GCA_900149125.1	Sollars et al (2017) Nature [doi.org/10.1038/nature20786]
<i>Fraxinus albicans</i>	FRAX26 1901-4706	Project: PRJEB20151	GCA_903798335.1	Kelly et al (2020) Nature Ecology & Evolution [doi.org/10.1038/s41559-020-1209-3]
<i>Fraxinus americana</i>	FRAX14 am-6 B	Project: PRJEB20151	GCA_903798225.1	Kelly et al (2020) Nature Ecology & Evolution [doi.org/10.1038/s41559-020-1209-3]
<i>Fraxinus angustifolia</i> subsp. <i>angustifolia</i>	FRAX01 56.017	Project: PRJEB20151	GCA_902829175.1	Kelly et al (2020) Nature Ecology & Evolution [doi.org/10.1038/s41559-020-1209-3]
<i>Fraxinus angustifolia</i> subsp. <i>oxycarpa</i>	FRAX15 31.077	Project: PRJEB20151	GCA_903798265.1	Kelly et al (2020) Nature Ecology & Evolution [doi.org/10.1038/s41559-020-1209-3]
<i>Fraxinus angustifolia</i> subsp. <i>syriaca</i>	FRAX16 1982-8111	Project: PRJEB20151	GCA_903798275.1	Kelly et al (2020) Nature Ecology & Evolution [doi.org/10.1038/s41559-020-1209-3]
<i>Fraxinus anomala</i>	FRAX27 ano-1	Project: PRJEB20151	GCA_903798345.1	Kelly et al (2020) Nature Ecology & Evolution [doi.org/10.1038/s41559-020-1209-3]
<i>Fraxinus apertisquamifera</i>	FRAX02 20071420-L	N/A	N/A	Unpublished
<i>Fraxinus baroniana</i>	FRAX28 bar-2	Project: PRJEB20151	GCA_903798355.1	Kelly et al (2020) Nature Ecology & Evolution [doi.org/10.1038/s41559-020-1209-3]

<i>Fraxinus biltmoreana</i>	FRAX17 5.0463	N/A	N/A	Unpublished
<i>Fraxinus chinensis</i> subsp. <i>rhynchophylla</i>	FRAX18 56.0651	N/A	N/A	Unpublished
<i>Fraxinus cuspidata</i>	FRAX31 cusp-5	Project: PRJEB20151	GCA_903798385.1	Kelly et al (2020) Nature Ecology & Evolution [doi.org/10.1038/s41559-020-1209-3]
<i>Fraxinus dipetala</i>	FRAX04 20080822-G	Project: PRJEB20151	GCA_902829195.1	Kelly et al (2020) Nature Ecology & Evolution [doi.org/10.1038/s41559-020-1209-3]
<i>Fraxinus floribunda</i>	FRAX32 flor-ins-12	Project: PRJEB20151	GCA_903798395.1	Kelly et al (2020) Nature Ecology & Evolution [doi.org/10.1038/s41559-020-1209-3]
<i>Fraxinus goodingii</i>	FRAX19 2011-1488	Project: PRJEB20151	GCA_903798285.1	Kelly et al (2020) Nature Ecology & Evolution [doi.org/10.1038/s41559-020-1209-3]
<i>Fraxinus greggii</i>	FRAX20 greg-1	Project: PRJEB20151	GCA_903798315.1	Kelly et al (2020) Nature Ecology & Evolution [doi.org/10.1038/s41559-020-1209-3]
<i>Fraxinus griffithii</i>	FRAX21 2011/18.O-B	Project: PRJEB20151	GCA_903798305.1	Kelly et al (2020) Nature Ecology & Evolution [doi.org/10.1038/s41559-020-1209-3]
<i>Fraxinus lanuginosa</i>	FRAX22 20071295 G	N/A	N/A	Unpublished
<i>Fraxinus latifolia</i>	FRAX05 56.0322	Project: PRJEB20151	GCA_902829145.1	Kelly et al (2020) Nature Ecology & Evolution [doi.org/10.1038/s41559-020-1209-3]
<i>Fraxinus mandschurica</i>	FRAX06 56.0269	Project: PRJEB20151	GCA_903772985.1	Kelly et al (2020) Nature Ecology & Evolution [doi.org/10.1038/s41559-020-1209-3]
<i>Fraxinus nigra</i>	FRAX23 19880480-C	Project: PRJEB20151	GCA_903798295.1	Kelly et al (2020) Nature Ecology & Evolution [doi.org/10.1038/s41559-020-1209-3]
<i>Fraxinus ornus</i>	FRAX07 32.0221	Project: PRJEB20151	GCA_903798235.1	Kelly et al (2020) Nature Ecology & Evolution [doi.org/10.1038/s41559-020-1209-3]
<i>Fraxinus paxiana</i>	FRAX08 56.0587	Project: PRJEB20151	GCA_902829205.1	Kelly et al (2020) Nature Ecology & Evolution [doi.org/10.1038/s41559-020-1209-3]
<i>Fraxinus profunda</i>	FRAX24 56.0568	N/A	N/A	Unpublished
<i>F. pennsylvanica</i> [was <i>F. caroliniana</i>]	FRAX03 56.0410	Project: PRJEB20151	GCA_902829185.1	Kelly et al (2020) Nature Ecology & Evolution [doi.org/10.1038/s41559-020-1209-3]
<i>Fraxinus pennsylvanica</i>	FRAX09 PE_00248	Project: PRJEB20151	GCA_903798245.1	Kelly et al (2020) Nature Ecology & Evolution

				[doi.org/10.1038/s41559-020-1209-3]
<i>Fraxinus pennsylvanica</i>	FRAX10 PE_48	Project: PRJEB20151	GCA_902829155.1	Kelly et al (2020) Nature Ecology & Evolution [doi.org/10.1038/s41559-020-1209-3]
<i>Fraxinus platypoda</i>	FRAX33 spa-1	Project: PRJEB20151	GCA_903798405.1	Kelly et al (2020) Nature Ecology & Evolution [doi.org/10.1038/s41559-020-1209-3]
<i>Fraxinus quadrangulata</i>	FRAX11 28.0230	Project: PRJEB20151	GCA_903798255.1	Kelly et al (2020) Nature Ecology & Evolution [doi.org/10.1038/s41559-020-1209-3]
<i>Fraxinus sieboldiana</i>	FRAX12 32.0516	Project: PRJEB20151	GCA_902876705.1	Kelly et al (2020) Nature Ecology & Evolution [doi.org/10.1038/s41559-020-1209-3]
<i>Fraxinus uhdei</i>	FRAX34 uhdei-ponto	N/A	N/A	Unpublished
<i>Fraxinus velutina</i>	FRAX13 56.0256	Project: PRJEB20151	GCA_902837555.1	Kelly et al (2020) Nature Ecology & Evolution [doi.org/10.1038/s41559-020-1209-3]
<i>Fraxinus xanthoxyloides</i>	FRAX25 19841432-C	Project: PRJEB20151	GCA_903798325.1	Kelly et al (2020) Nature Ecology & Evolution [doi.org/10.1038/s41559-020-1209-3]
<i>Fraxinus</i> sp. 1973-6204 [previously <i>F. bungeana</i>]	FRAX29 1973-6204	Project: PRJEB20151	GCA_903798365.1	Kelly et al (2020) Nature Ecology & Evolution [doi.org/10.1038/s41559-020-1209-3]
<i>Fraxinus</i> sp. D2006-0159 [previously <i>chinensis</i> subsp. <i>chinensis</i>]	FRAX30 F-unk-1	Project: PRJEB20151	GCA_903798375.1	Kelly et al (2020) Nature Ecology & Evolution [doi.org/10.1038/s41559-020-1209-3]

Table 2: Transcriptome data

Species	Description (tissue type, accession)	Reads on ENA	Publication
<i>Fraxinus excelsior</i>	Leaf transcriptome 2451S	Project: PRJEB4958 Sample: ERS370607 Experiments: ERX1470832	Sollars et al (2017) Nature [doi.org/10.1038/nature20786]
<i>Fraxinus excelsior</i>	Root, leaf, cambium and flower transcriptomes of parent of 2451S	Project: PRJEB4958 Sample: ERS1138331 Experiments: ERX147051-ERX147054	Sollars et al (2017) Nature [doi.org/10.1038/nature20786]
<i>Fraxinus mandshurica</i>	FRAX06 56.0269 various tissues	N/A	unpublished
<i>Fraxinus ornus</i>	FRAX07 32.0221 various tissues	N/A	unpublished
<i>Fraxinus quadrangulata</i>	FRAX11 28.0230 various tissues	N/A	unpublished
<i>Fraxinus gooddingii</i>	FRAX19 2011-1488 various tissues	N/A	unpublished

Table 3. Re-sequence data

Species	Description	Reads on ENA	Publication
<i>Fraxinus excelsior</i>	Diversity Panel (37 trees from across Europe, 8.4X coverage)	Project: PRJEB4958 Samples: ERS1205907-ERS1205943 Experiments: ERX1527454; ERX1527519- ERX1527532; ERX1527545- ERX1527554; ERX1527557- ERX1527568; ERX1527570- ERX1527606	Sollars et al (2017) Nature [doi.org/10.1038/nature20786]
<i>Fraxinus excelsior</i>	31 Pools (80X coverage) from 1250 trees	Project: PRJEB31096	Stocks et al (2019) Nature Ecology & Evolution [doi.org/10.1038/s41559-019-1036-6]
<i>Fraxinus excelsior</i>	150 individuals (20X coverage)	Project: PRJEB31096	Stocks et al (2019) Nature Ecology & Evolution [doi.org/10.1038/s41559-019-1036-6]
<i>Fraxinus excelsior</i>	660 individuals (Marden Park Wood)	N/A	Unpublished

Table 4: Bisulfite sequence data

Species	Description	Reads on ENA	Publication
<i>Fraxinus excelsior</i>	Bisulphite WGS (Danish Clones 27, 33, 35, 40)	Project: PRJEB4958 Samples: ERS1887564-ERS1887583 Experiments: ERX2162802-ERX2162821	Sollars et al (2018) BMC Genomics [doi.org/10.1186/s12864-018-4874-8]
<i>Fraxinus mandschurica</i>	Bisulphite WGS (2 Danish samples)	Project: PRJEB4958 Samples: ERS1887564-ERS1887566 Experiments: ERX2162802-ERX2162821	Sollars et al (2018) BMC Genomics [doi.org/10.1186/s12864-018-4874-8]